

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Unveiling the advances and challenges in the development of Er³⁺-doped tellurite fiber with embedded Ag nanoparticles

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Abstract

Er³⁺-doped fibers are widely used as 1.55 μm broadband optical amplifiers. Tellurite glasses are particularly suitable as a gain medium due to their lower phonon energy and better rare-earth solubility compared to silica glass. Various strategies, such as reducing the OH content and co-doping with silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs), are attempted to improve the spectroscopic properties. However, maintaining the glass drawability into fibers when developing glasses with improved spectroscopic properties remains a significant challenge. Indeed, it is confirmed that NH₄HF₂ can be added into the tellurite glass batch prior to the melting to reduce OH⁻ content. However, the presence of remaining F in the glass is demonstrated to have a detrimental impact on the glass thermal properties preventing the drawing of this glass into fiber. The successful drawing of a single-index optical fiber from a tellurite glass preform heavily doped with Er³⁺ ions is reported for the first time. The Ag NPs are grown in the fiber using a thermal treatment at the glass transition temperature. The presence of the NPs is confirmed using a TEM and from the spectroscopic properties. The interaction between Er³⁺ ions and the Ag species offers potential for modifying the luminescence properties of the fiber.

KEYWORDS

erbium, fiber, OH reduction, silver nanoparticles, tellurite glasses

1 | INTRODUCTION

Rare-earth (RE) ions have become essential elements in the development of high-tech products. Among these elements, erbium has been of particular interest. The trivalent erbium ions (Er³⁺) can be used to achieve emissions in

the visible, near-infrared (NIR), and mid-infrared (MIR) regions due to its unique energy level structure.^{1–3} Doping silica glass with Er³⁺ ions creates an active glass, which, when drawn into fiber, can find uses in a variety of applications, such as telecommunication, light sources, detection, and so forth.^{1,4} For lasing application, for

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example, the fiber needs to have high gain coefficient, which can be obtained by increasing the Er^{3+} concentration. However, the solubility of RE ions in silica network is limited, leading to RE clustering and, consequently, to luminescence quenching when introducing RE in high concentration.^{5,6}

As the solubility of the RE ions in the glass network depends on the glass host, other glass systems have been intensively investigated such as fluoride,⁷ phosphate,⁸ germanate,⁹ and tellurite¹⁰ for the development of new active glasses with enhanced spectroscopic properties. Compared to silica glass, tellurite glasses are promising materials due to their wider infrared transmission window and lower phonon energy. Additionally, they can be prepared at lower melting temperatures and can incorporate higher concentration of RE ions without forming RE clusters.¹¹ As most glasses, the composition of tellurite glasses can be easily tailored so glasses can be prepared with improved chemical, optical, and mechanical properties as well as enhanced spectroscopic properties, making tellurite glasses promising materials for lasing applications. Recently, Lemiere et al. reported a complete study on the impact of tellurite glass composition on the spectroscopic properties of Er^{3+} ions.¹² Although no changes in the sites of Er^{3+} ions were reported when adding Na_2O , Bi_2O_3 , or BaO in the TeO_2 - ZnO glass system, better spectroscopic properties were obtained from the glass prepared with Bi_2O_3 due to its low OH^- groups content known as a serious Er^{3+} luminescence quenchers.¹³ Efforts have been focused on developing techniques such as purification and dehydration to reduce OH^- content in glasses. Massera et al. demonstrated a 93% reduction in the OH^- content in tellurite glass by drying the batch with fluorine-based raw materials before melting and using O_2 -rich atmosphere during the melting.¹⁴ However, reducing the OH^- content to improve the spectroscopic properties of the glass can impact various glass properties such as the thermal, physical, and structural properties.¹⁵ Therefore, it is essential to find other ways to improve the spectroscopic properties and so the gain coefficient of the glass fiber.

The other commonly used strategy is to couple the RE ions with noble metal nanoparticles (NPs) to induce modification of doped ligand environment.^{16,17} Indeed, metallic NPs express unique light-scattering characteristics, based on a strong localized electric field induced by the oscillation of the collective charge density at the NPs surface known as surface plasmon resonance (SPR), which depends on the NPs composition, size, and aggregation state.^{18,19} For instance, the enhancement of the glass spectroscopic properties can be obtained when coupling silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) with Er^{3+} ions due to the localized electric field and also due to the energy transfer

from the Ag NPs to the Er^{3+} ions.^{20,21} Glasses within various (silicate,²² phosphate,²³ and tellurite¹⁸) networks have been successfully prepared with embedded Ag NPs, which are usually grown using a two-step process: At first, metal ions are added into the glass network, and then a post-treatment (radiation^{24,25} or thermal treatment²⁶) is applied to form the NPs. Although many studies have been conducted on the growth of metallic NPs in glasses, fibers with embedded metallic NPs have not been extensively developed yet due to different challenges, the main one being related to maintaining the integrity of the NPs in the fiber. Most of the investigations have focused on silica fiber, which were heat-treated before or after the drawing to grow NPs.^{25,27} For example, enhancement in the spectroscopic properties of germanosilicate fiber was reported when co-doping the glass with Au NPs and Er^{3+} ions.²⁸ Surprisingly, no studies on Er^{3+} -doped tellurite fiber with embedded Ag NPs have been reported as of today, to the best of our knowledge.

Here, we report a study on unveiling the enhancement of the spectroscopic properties of Er^{3+} -doped tellurite glasses in the TeO_2 - ZnO - Bi_2O_3 system using different approaches: the reduction in the content of the OH groups and the growth of Ag NPs using thermal treatment. We demonstrate that a fiber with embedded Ag NPs can be drawn from a preform offering attractive functions in the field related to fiber lasers and amplifiers.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Synthesis of samples

Tellurite glasses with the composition 65.45TeO_2 - 18.70ZnO - $9.35\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ - $4\text{Ag}_2\text{O}$ - $2.5\text{Er}_2\text{O}_3$ (in mol%) were synthesized by the standard melt-quenching method and subsequent release stress process. The raw materials of TeO_2 (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), ZnO (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), Bi_2O_3 (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), Er_2O_3 (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), and Ag_2SO_4 (Honeywell, 99.5%) were well mixed with a mortar and pestle. The uniformly mixed stoichiometric compounds were put into a quartz crucible and melted at 775°C for 40 min in air atmosphere. Batches were prepared without (labeled X0) and with 2 wt% of NH_4HF_2 (Sigma-Aldrich, 98.5%) (labeled X2). Prior to melting the X2 batch, a preheat treatment at 500°C for 1 h was used to evaporate the fluorine. After melting, the glass melt was poured onto a brass plate and annealed in a muffle furnace at 40°C below glass transition temperature (T_g) for 5 h to release the stress. Finally, the glasses were cut and polished to perform the spectroscopic measurement. Ag NPs were grown in the glasses by heat treating the glasses at T_g for 72 and 96 h.

2.2 | Preform preparation and fiber drawing

A 10-cm long preform with 1 cm diameter was prepared from X0 glass. The drawing process was conducted at 455°C under a helium gas flow of 1.5 L/min to maintain an inert atmosphere and homogeneous thermal profile in the furnace. One can note that the furnace temperature is always higher than the temperature seen by the glass during the drawing process. In this work, the temperature seen by the glass is estimated by 400–410°C, which is lower than the onset crystallization temperature of the glass (T_x 444°C). No coating was applied during the drawing process, to allow for the measurement of the thermal and structural properties of the fiber pieces. A few-meter-long fiber with a diameter of ~ 150 μm was obtained. The fiber pieces were thermally treated at T_g for 72 and 96 h to grow the NPs.

2.3 | Characterization of samples

The refractive indices with an accuracy of ± 0.001 were measured at 443, 633, 825, 1061, 1312, and 1533 nm using the prism coupling technique using the Abbe refractometer (Model 2010/M, Metricon). Ten scans were performed for each wavelength.

The glass transition and crystallization temperatures were obtained from the thermograms using the differential thermal analysis (DTA, Netzsch Jupiter F1 instrument). The measurements were carried out in a platinum crucible with a heating rate of 10°C/min. The glass transition temperature (T_g) was taken as the inflection point of the endotherm peaks by taking the first derivative of the DTA curve, whereas T_x and T_p were obtained from the onset and maximum of the exothermic peak, respectively. The thermal stability of the glasses against crystallization was estimated based on the difference between the glass transition and onset crystallization temperatures $\Delta T = T_x - T_g$. All measurements were performed with an accuracy of $\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$.

Raman spectra were measured using the Renishaw inVia Qontor Raman microscope equipped with a cooled charge-coupled device camera. A 785-nm laser was used as an excitation source.

The absorption spectra of the bulk glasses were measured using the UV–vis–NIR spectrophotometer (UV-3600 Plus, Shimadzu) within a wavelength range of 250–1800 nm and measurement step of 1 nm. The absorption cross-section $\sigma_{\text{abs}}(\lambda)$ was calculated with an accuracy of $\pm 10\%$ using the following equation:

$$\sigma_{\text{abs}}(\lambda) = \frac{\ln 10D(\lambda)}{NL} \quad (1)$$

where $D(\lambda)$ is the absorbance, N is the concentration of Er^{3+} ions in the glass (ions/cm³), and L is the thickness of the sample.

The transmission of the fiber from 600 to 1700 nm was measured by launching light from a white light source (MG922A, Anritsu) with a 105- μm multimode fiber butt-coupled to the sample fiber. The IR absorption spectra were measured using the FTIR2000 PerkinElmer spectrometer in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode with a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ and accumulation of eight scans.

The emission spectra of the bulk samples, related to the Er^{3+} spectroscopic properties, were measured at room temperature using a continuous-wave 980 nm monochromatic single-mode fiber-pigtailed laser diode (CM962UF76P-10R, Oclaro) for excitation. The upconversion and NIR emission spectra were acquired using a spectro 320-131 optical spectrum analyzer (Instrument Systems Optische Messtechnik GmbH). The MIR emission spectra in the range of 2500–3000 nm were collected using a monochromator coupled with an amplified MIR detector (detector PCI-4TE-4-1 \times 1, preamplifier PIP-DC-200 M-F-M4, Vigo).

The emission and excitation spectra related to the Ag spectroscopic properties were measured using Edinburgh FLS1000 photoluminescence spectrometer using a xenon lamp as an excitation source.

The emission spectra of the fiber were measured using the fiber-pigtailed 980 nm laser diode (Coherent). The output light was collected with a 200 μm multimode fiber and analyzed using an OSA (ANDO AQ6317B).

The gain cross-section of the glass was calculated for different levels of population inversion using following equation:

$$\sigma_g(\lambda, \beta) = \beta\sigma_{em}(\lambda) - (1 - \beta)\sigma_{abs}(\lambda) \quad (2)$$

where $\beta = N_{ex}/N_{tot}$ is the population inversion parameter, N_{ex} is the population density of the excited state $^4I_{13/2}$, and N_{tot} is the total Er^{3+} ion concentration.

The stimulated emission cross-section spectrum $\sigma_{em}(\lambda)$ in the NIR region is derived from the emission spectra $I(\lambda)$ by the Fuchtbauer–Landenburg theory through the following formula:²⁹

$$\sigma_{em}(\lambda) = \frac{\lambda^4 A}{8\pi cn^2} \frac{I(\lambda)}{\int I(\lambda) d\lambda}, \quad (3)$$

where n is the refractive index of the glass at wavelength λ , c is the speed of light, A is radiation transition probability from the excited state $^4I_{13/2}$ to the ground state $^4I_{15/2}$ and can be calculated using the absorption spectrum as

FIGURE 1 The effect of the addition of NH_4HF_2 to the tellurite glass system on the optical, structural, and spectroscopic properties. X0 is the parent glass, and X2 is the glass prepared by adding NH_4HF_2 in the glass batch prior to the melting. (A) Infrared (IR) absorption spectra measured in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode. (B) Upconversion emission spectra of the investigated glasses, obtained under excitation at 980 nm, the bands at ~ 525 , 545, and 660 nm correspond to the Er^{3+} transitions from ${}^2\text{H}_{11/2}$, ${}^4\text{S}_{3/2}$, and ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$ to the ground state ${}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$, respectively. (C) Near-infrared (NIR) emission spectra of the investigated glasses under excitation at 980 nm showing an emission band which corresponds to the $\text{Er}^{3+} {}^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transition. (D) Mid-infrared (MIR) emission spectra of the investigated glasses under excitation at 980 nm showing an emission band that corresponds to the $\text{Er}^{3+} {}^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transition. (E) Raman spectra of the investigated glasses, obtained at excitation wavelength of 532 nm. (F) Refractive index dispersion of the investigated glasses.

follows:³⁰

$$A = \frac{2J' + 1}{2J + 1} \frac{8\pi c n^2}{\lambda^4} \int \sigma_{\text{abs}}(\lambda) d\lambda, \quad (4)$$

where J and J' are the total angular momenta of the upper and lower levels. $\int \sigma_{\text{abs}}(\lambda) d\lambda$ is the integrated absorption cross-section of the band centered at 1.5 μm .

The amorphous structure of the glasses was identified using the x-ray diffractometer (XRD) analyzer (PANalytical Empyrean) with $\text{Cu } K_{\alpha}$ x-ray radiation ($\lambda = 0.15405$ nm) in the 2θ range from 10° to 70° with a step size of 0.05° .

The glass surface was analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Crossbeam 540 Carl Zeiss) equipped with an energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS/EDX) detector (Oxford Instruments X-MaxN 80). The samples were mounted on Al-stubs and coated with a thin carbon layer prior to the SEM analysis. The microscopy images were obtained by a Tecnai microscope (G20, 200 kV), whereas the elemental mapping was obtained by the energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy analysis. A transmission electron microscope (TECNAI G20) with a

resolution of 0.2 nm and voltage acceleration of 200 kV was used to obtain the microstructure and to verify the existence Ag NPs in the glass matrix and fiber. The fine powder of glass was dispersed in acetone and isolated by an ultrasonic bath for about 20 min. A drop of solution was spatted on the copper grid and dried before analysis.

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Er^{3+} -doped tellurite glasses have been considered promising candidates for 1.55 μm broadband optical amplifier,³¹ especially the 65.45 TeO_2 –18.70 ZnO –9.35 Bi_2O_3 –4 Ag_2O –2.5 Er_2O_3 glass composition (in mol%),³² labeled a parent glass X0. It is well known that the spectroscopic properties of such glasses can be enhanced by reducing the OH^- group content in the glass network.¹³ Here, the glass was prepared by adding 2 wt% of NH_4HF_2 in the glass batch prior to the melting and labeled X2 (see Section 2.1), as Massera et al. did to reduce the OH^- content following the reaction $\text{OH}^- + \text{F}^- \rightarrow \text{HF} + \text{O}^{2-}$.^{14,33} The OH^- reduction when using NH_4HF_2 was confirmed from the reduction in

FIGURE 2 The absorption spectra of the X0 (A) and X2 (B) glasses prior to and after heat treatment at T_g for 72 and 96 h.

TABLE 1 Thermal properties of the investigated glasses.

Code	T_g ($\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$)	T_x ($\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$)	T_p ($\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$)	$\Delta T = T_x - T_g$ ($\pm 6^\circ\text{C}$)
X0	332	444	473	112
X2	320	378	390	58

intensity of the absorption bands in the 2000–3500 cm^{-1} range (Figure 1A), which is attributed to the “free” OH^- groups (weakly associated) with a band at $\sim 3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, “strongly” hydrogen bonded OH^- groups with absorption bands at $\sim 2800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (strongly associated), and “very strongly” hydrogen bonded OH^- groups with the absorption band at 2350 cm^{-1} (very strongly associated).^{34,35} As expected, the reduction of the OH^- content increases the intensity of the emissions in the visible, NIR, and MIR (Figure 1B–D). However, the use of NH_4HF_2 leads to minor changes in the glass structure as evidenced in Figure 1E. The Raman spectra of the glasses are similar to those reported by Lemiere et al.¹² A complete characterization of the structural properties can be found in this work. The reduction in the OH^- content leads to an increase in the intensity of the Raman bands at 400 and 660 cm^{-1} as compared to the main band at 740 cm^{-1} , suggesting an increase in the O–Te–O and Te–O–Bi linkages and in the number TeO_4 units at the expense of $\text{TeO}_3/\text{TeO}_{3+1}$ units, respectively.^{36–38} This increase in the polymerization of tellurite network induced by the change of coordination from $\text{TeO}_3/\text{TeO}_{3+1}$ units to TeO_4 units when reducing the OH^- content leads to a reduction in the refractive index (Figure 1F) although Capanema et al. reported an increase in the refractive index associated with the polymerization of the tellurite network.³⁹ They also reported that the changes in the glass structure increase T_g and T_x . Here, the reduction in the OH^- content reduces the T_g and T_x as well as the T_p despite the formation of a more polymerized glass (Table 1). It is the presence of residual F^- ($\sim 2.5 \text{ at}\%$) in the glass network as checked using EPMA, which is expected to reduce the refractive index

of the glass and also the thermal properties, including ΔT , commonly used to gauge the glass thermal stability against crystallization.⁴⁰ Although the presence of F^- changes slightly the glass network, it has no significant impact on the site of the Er^{3+} ions as the X0 and X2 glasses exhibit similar shape of emission bands (Figure 1B–D). No changes in the absorption spectra were observed (Figure S1). It is worth to mention that the X0 and X2 glasses exhibit similar absorption ($8.03 \times 10^{-21} \text{ cm}^2$) and emission ($6.84 \times 10^{-21} \text{ cm}^2$) cross-sections, within $\pm 10\%$, in agreement with those reported for tellurite glasses.¹²

It is well known that the spectroscopic properties of Er^{3+} -doped glass can also be enhanced using Ag NPs with strong plasmon absorption.⁴¹ The thermal treatment of the as-prepared glass can be performed in order to precipitate the Ag NPs.⁴² Here, the glasses were heat-treated for 72 and 96 h at their respective T_g to avoid inducing crystallization of the network during the thermal treatment, which was confirmed from the XRD pattern of the heat-treated glasses (Figure S2). The XRD patterns of the heat-treated glasses did not show the characteristic diffraction lines from metallic Ag NPs. However, the precipitation of the Ag NPs was confirmed from the absorption spectra of the heat-treated glasses (Figure 2A,B). Indeed, an absorption band in the 400–600 nm, which overlaps with the Er^{3+} absorption bands, appears in the absorption spectrum of both glasses after the thermal treatment. A slight increase in the intensity of this band is suspected to occur when the duration of the thermal treatment increases. This band can be related to the SPR band of the Ag NPs,⁴³ suggesting that the volume fraction of the Ag NPs is probably too small to be detected in the XRD pattern. Both glasses exhibit a similar SPR band (position and intensity within $\pm 10\%$) after thermal treatment.

Based on the position of this SPR band, a size of 20–40 nm is expected for the Ag NPs according to Soltani et al.,⁴⁴ which is confirmed using TEM. According to the TEM images (Figure 3), Ag NPs with an average size of ~ 16 and $\sim 18 \text{ nm}$ precipitate in X0 and X2 glasses during the

FIGURE 3 TEM images of the X0 and X2 glasses prior to and after heat treatment at T_g for 72 and 96 h.

thermal treatment for 72 h, suggesting that slightly larger Ag NPs might precipitate in the X2 glasses. However, no size distribution can be provided as the number of the Ag NPs found in the samples was only ~ 30 , knowing that at least 100 NPs are usually needed to obtain a reliable size distribution histogram. Additionally, one should be careful when discussing the size of the Ag NPs as these NPs were found unstable under the electron beams. They tend to diffuse, merge, or disappear during the collection of the TEM images. Nonetheless, we can expect a slight growth of the Ag NPs size ($\sim +2$ nm) and number when increasing the duration of the thermal treatment from 72 to 96 h. Additionally, one should mention that a few Ag species, such as nanoclusters or small NPs (size of ~ 5 nm), are already observed in the as-prepared X0 glass. None were seen in the as-prepared X2 glass, but it does not indicate that there are no nanoclusters or small NPs in this as-prepared glass as a small volume of glass is used for the TEM analysis.

As expected, the precipitation of the Ag NPs in the glass has an impact on the Er^{3+} spectroscopic properties (Figure S3A–F). However, a decrease in the intensity of the UC and emission bands at 1.55 and 2.7 μm is observed after the thermal treatment and should be related to the large amount of Ag_2O in the glasses that induces the reverse energy transfer from Er^{3+} ions to Ag NPs.⁴⁵

In order to evaluate the interaction of the Ag species with Er^{3+} ions, a deeper attention is paid to the spectroscopic properties of the Ag species. Excitation spectra of the glasses were collected at a wavelength of 460 nm, for which no absorption or emission from Er^{3+} is observed

to discriminate the contribution of Er^{3+} ions from that of the Ag species (Figure 4A). The excitation spectra show a wide band, covering the wavelength range 330–430 nm which can be assigned mainly to Ag_m^{n+} .⁴⁶ The dip at 380 nm is related to Er^{3+} absorption of the excitation beam, which corresponds to the $^4\text{I}_{15/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{G}_{11/2}$ transition. After the thermal treatment, the intensity of the excitation band increases suggesting that the thermal treatment leads to the formation of more Ag_m^{n+} species.^{46,47}

The spectroscopic properties of the Ag NPs and nanoclusters are known to depend on the excitation wavelengths depending on the type of Ag species being excited. The emission spectra of the investigated glasses were measured using different excitation wavelengths (250, 355, and 428 nm) (Figure 4B). Under excitation at 250 nm, a wide emission band (300–600 nm) appears with two bands at 290 and 420 nm, which can be assigned to the emission from Ag^+ and $(\text{Ag}^+)_2$, respectively.^{45–47} The tail of the emission band at 420 nm in the longer wavelength range can be related to the emission from the Ag_m^{n+} species. This emission band covering the wavelength range 400–500 nm is clearly visible when using an excitation at 355 nm. Increasing the thermal treatment duration leads to an increase in the overall intensity of the emission bands obtained when using excitation at 250 and 355 nm with an enhancement of the right-side bands suggesting not only an increase in the Ag clusters' number but also in their size during longer thermal treatment as suspected from the TEM images (Figure 3). The spectra also show the typical emission band of Er^{3+} at 525, 550, and 650 nm, related

FIGURE 4 Ag spectroscopic properties in the glasses X0 and X2. (A) The excitation spectra of the X0 and X2 glasses, prior to and after heat treatment at T_g for 72 and 96 h for emission at 460 nm. (B) The emission spectra of the X0 and X2 glasses prior to and after heat treatment at T_g for 72 and 96 h for excitation at 250, 355, and 428 nm.

to the $2H_{11/2}$, $4S_{3/2} \rightarrow 4I_{15/2}$, and $4F_{9/2} \rightarrow 4I_{15/2}$ transitions, respectively. However, under excitation at 250 nm, only weak contribution from the Er^{3+} ions is detected. According to Kalkman et al., the electric dipole transition of Er^{3+} ions is sensitive to the local field.⁴⁸ When the distance between silver species and Er^{3+} ions is short enough, the surrounding Er^{3+} ions can be activated, enhancing the electronic excitation efficiency. However, after the thermal treatment and the growth of silver species in the vicinity of Er^{3+} ions, this distance is expected to become shorter. As a consequence, it is possible that inverse energy transfer occurs from excited states of Er^{3+} ions to the silver species leading to the reduction in the intensity of the Er^{3+} emissions in the visible under 355 nm excitation after the thermal treatment as seen in Figure 4B. As observed in Pr^{3+}/Yb^{3+} co-doped fluorophosphate glass prepared with $AgNO_3$,⁴⁶ the silver species in the as-prepared and heat-treated glasses could be used to excite the Er^{3+} ions at wavelength of 355 nm. However, when the excitation is at 428 nm, competitive absorptions from Er^{3+} are seen in the broad emission band, which ranges from 400 to 900 nm. Due to the low intensity of these emission bands after 428 nm excitation from the X2 glasses, a more efficient radiative energy transfer and reabsorption by Er^{3+} ions are expected to occur in the X2 glasses than in the X0 glasses. It is interesting to point out that the intensity of the shoulder in the 600–900 nm range increases after the thermal treatment confirming the growth in size and in number of the Ag clusters during thermal treatment. One should

mention that from the comparison of the intensity of the emission bands from the X0 and X2 glasses, a higher number of larger Ag clusters is suspected to form in the most polymerized glass (X2 glass with lower amount of OH-content).

A single-index fiber with a diameter of 150 μm (no cladding) was successfully drawn from the X0 glass, the chosen composition as this glass is the most thermally stable against crystallization as evidenced by its large ΔT ($> 100^\circ C$) (Table 1).^{49,50} After the drawing process, the glass composition remains the same within the accuracy of the measurement (± 1.5 mol%) as checked using SEM/EDS cross-section line scan (Figure S4A). Furthermore, no clusters of the glass elements nor crystals were observed at the outer surface of the fiber (Figure S4B). Despite being a fast process, the drawing led to slight changes in the glass structure as depicted in Figure 5A. The small increase in intensity of the bands at ~ 400 and 660 cm^{-1} as compared to that of the main band suggests an increase in the O–Te–O and Te–O–Bi linkages and of the number TeO_4 units at the expense of TeO_3/TeO_{3+1} units, respectively, indicating the slight increase in the polymerization of the glass network after the drawing. Similar transformation of network during fiber drawing process was reported by Massera et al. and was related to the changes in the thermal history of the glass and the orientation of the molecular units in the network during the drawing process.⁵¹ Despite the changes in the glass network, no significant changes in the site of the Er^{3+} are expected to occur during drawing (Figure S4C).

FIGURE 5 The effect of the drawing and heat treatment on the structural and spectroscopic properties of the single-index fiber. (A) Raman spectra of the fiber and the preform. (B) The transmittance spectra of the as-drawn and heat-treated fiber pieces with a length of 60 mm. (C) The picture of the optical setup showing the injection of the 980 nm pumping into the fiber and the corresponding green upconversion from the fiber. (D) The emission spectra of the as-drawn and heat-treated fiber pieces with lengths ranging from 2 to 60 mm. The spectra were obtained using an excitation at 980 nm. (E) The calculated gain cross-section of the glass for different values of population inversion parameter.

Despite being a single-index fiber, light confinement in the as-drawn fiber was observed (Figure 5B,C). A green emission is noticeable by naked eye in the first few millimeters of the fiber when injecting the 980 nm pumping (Figure 5C). This green emission can be related to the upconversion process which is due to the high Er^{3+} concentration (2.5 mol%). As a result, significant changes in the shape of the emission band can be observed when testing the fiber pieces at different lengths. Indeed, a typical emission band of Er^{3+} ions due to the ${}^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transition is observed from the fiber with a length smaller than 2 mm (Figure 5D). However, reabsorption of the emission signal occurs in the fiber and starts to be dominant with a length >2 mm leading to significant changes in the shape of the emission band, which are similar to the changes in the shape of the calculated gain cross-section for the ${}^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transition for various population inversion values ranging from 0 to 1 (Figure 5E). Figure 5E clearly shows that signal amplification below 1650 nm could be achieved when population inversion is more than 60%.

As for the bulk, the fiber was thermally treated at its glass transition temperature for 72 and 96 h to promote the precipitation and growth of Ag NPs, which were confirmed using TEM (Figure 6). One should mention that Ag NPs are detected already in the as-drawn fiber as shown in Figure 6. A reduction in the transmittance after the thermal treatment is observed in Figure 5B and should be attributed not only to the precipitation of the Ag NPs and other silver species but also to the formation of defects on the surface of the uncoated fiber. No changes in the gain cross-section are suspected to occur after the thermal treatment. Note that the excitation and emission spectra of the heat-treated fiber could not be collected due to the low amount of glass from the fiber pieces when crushed into powder.

4 | CONCLUSION

In this study, we report a successful synthesis of single-index optical fiber from tellurite glass preform heavily doped with Er^{3+} ions. We test two methods that can be

FIGURE 6 TEM images of the as-drawn and heat-treated fiber prior to and after heat treatment at T_g for 72 and 96 h.

applied to improve the spectroscopic properties of Er^{3+} ions: co-doping with Ag NPs and reducing the OH^- content in the preform by adding NH_4HF_2 into the glass batch. It was found that adding NH_4HF_2 improves the spectroscopic properties of Er^{3+} ions in the visible, NIR, and MIR region, increases the glass polymerization, and promotes the growth of Ag species and Ag NPs in the glass upon heat treatment. However, the use of NH_4HF_2 leads to the presence of F^- ions in the glass network which reduces the thermal stability of the glass preventing the drawing of this glass into fiber. Nonetheless, a single-index fiber was successfully drawn from preform prepared without NH_4HF_2 .

This research demonstrates a proof-of-concept for the growth of Ag NPs in tellurite glass fiber using a thermal treatment, offering attractive promises for the development of fiber lasers and erbium-doped fiber amplifiers.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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